

THE POSSIBILITIES OF USING THE PEDAGOGICAL HERITAGE OF MAKHMUDKHOJA BEHBUDI IN THE SECONDARY CLASSES

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Abstract. *This article will explore the importance of ancient manuscripts by Behbudi and how to implement them in the process of education and teaching.*

Keywords: *geography, constitutional parliamentary authority, monarchy.*

In Mahmudhoji Behbudi's textbook "Book geography general", full title "Kitabi Muntahabi geography general and exemplary geography" ("selected book on general geography", 1906), he accused "scientists who do not know the new science" of creating an artificial barrier between secular and religious knowledge, discrediting Islam because of their ignorance. In this textbook, the author states: "If we do not study geography, we will not be able to advance into the world."

For the publication of this textbook, the author received permission from the St. Petersburg censorship on August 24, 1905, and in 1906 in Samarkand it was printed in the printing house of G.I. Demurov. The textbook consists of 106 pages. Its first pages cover the history of the emergence of geography as a science, the merits of scientists of ancient Turkestan in this field, and examples from their works are given. The author based his opinion on documents and evidence in the famous 6-volume "Qamus ul-Alam" by Shamsiddinbek Sami (1850-1904) and "Ulamosi of Turkestan" by I. Gasprinsky. The author very simply explains the location and movement of celestial bodies. The author's observations are more noticeable in the text entitled "Hukamo kavlich, signs of the roundness of the Earth". It compares the time of Petersburg and Tashkent with other cities of the world and two tables are attached.

Mahmudhoja divides the existing management methods of Behbudi times into three:

- independent office (monarchy);
- odorai mashruta (constitutional parliamentary authority);
- office Republic (Republic). He also notes that people are divided into races: white, black, red and yellow.

The heliocentric structure of the movement of the Earth, the construction of the world and its representatives in European science N. Copernicus, Kepler, It tells about the activities of G.Galileo.

In this textbook, the author writes: "...Editing and summarizing this book, "Muntahabi geographi General", we have included in it expositions and quotations from educational, mathematical, religious, omnibus, political and biblical religion. The summary and detailed information about science were classified in Turkic, Arabic, Persian, Russian dictionaries containing up to thirty ancient and Jadid manuscripts, and each of these dictionaries "Gazit-Jarida, atlas, map, Kurrai Mumuttaha, statistical complexes jam' and ordered".

The tutorial contains an introduction on the page. The first topic in it is called "geography".

At this point, the author defines the word geography, breaking it into several sections. That is, "mathematical geography", "natural geography", "historical geography", "political geography",

"lifelong geography", etc. He will elaborate on the meaning of geography in the final part of the textbook. "When was geography born? under the heading "When did this science arise and develop?" some thoughts about its development are presented. This section provides information about geographers and their works.

M.Behbudi tried to present information about celestial bodies, the rotation of the Earth in a language suitable for children. There are also many books on geography written in the textbook, there are treatises by Abulkasim Ubaydullah "Kitab al-masolik wa-l-mamolik" and "Kitab as-samo", they are translated into French and German, scientists who have contributed to the development of geography, their works, the discovery of the American continent, seas, straits, Russia and others . Detailed information is provided about the countries of Europe where geographical science is still in development.

The next section of the textbook is called "Turkestan sages", it contains hundreds of works by Muslim scholars Ibn Sina on vocabulary, logic, geography, music, ethics, chemistry, abtoli akhkomi nujum, nature, wisdom, medicine, they are translated into European languages, Badriddin Samarqandi, Abdurakhman Khorezmi, Abu Yazid Balkhi, Abdurakhman Such sages Like Marwazi, Abdurazzak Herati, Abu Ibrahim Gurgani, Sharif Khorezmi, Ahmad bin Tabib Sarahsi, Abu Mashar Balkhi, Abu Jafar Khorezmi, Ahmad Ferghani, information is given about the direction in which they worked, and the dates when they lived and worked are given.

Under the title "the study of geography" the author reflects on the importance of geographical education and its role in the development of personality. He says, among other things: "... Religion and sect of the people of the world, life and dam, the cause of progress and decline, good and evil, peace and quiet of countries or oppression and tyranny, conclusion, is a science that expresses the whole state of the world, the power of kings, the state, the customs of people, the state of the earth."

One of the notable and necessary sections of the textbook for that time was called "Muslims need to read geography."

In this section, the author discusses the fallacy of looking at the earth bearing the horn of a bull, that a person who has studied geography well knows that it is round. In this section, the author emphasizes the deep study of geography in countries such as Istanbul, Egypt, Arabia, India, Russia.

The teacher of enlightenment in this textbook also touches on the "old and new sages", emphasizing that "old sages" should be called ancient Greek scientists, and "new" - European scientists. Explaining to readers his views on the earth on the basis of mutual comparisons, he notes similarities with the opinions of Europeans. Under the heading "an example from the new word hakamasari" tells about the rotation of the Earth around the Sun, about how the stars receive light from the sun, about the planet mirrix (Mars), which also has soil, rocks, grass, water, clouds, rain and snow. It is worth noting that the author made a mistake in this place. Because the author: people live on Mars, and their knowledge is superior to ours, if you look through binoculars, you can see the waters of rivers, Mars is six times smaller than Earth and has day and night, winter and summer. In 1346, Neptune was discovered, whose distance from the sun was 4175 million light-years. a mile, he writes. He also mentions the age of the Earth in the textbook. An interesting topic for readers is the textbook entitled "When the Earth rotates, and does not fall on it", which examines the gravity of the Earth.

The next topic is "Environment, the aspect is original, map, plan". It is called about what the author thinks about the north, south, west, east sides and the compass. To work with a map, to create a map, thousands of masters, engineers, tourists have been measuring and writing for 500 years. It focuses on such things as natural map, bahria map, agricultural map, ethnographic map, etc. If several such maps are collected and made into a book, an atlas can be formed.

In the section of the textbook entitled "government and rulers", the author writes: "Bedouin and cultural peoples on Earth will be rulers and captains, who will be called beks, amirs, kings and other names and dictionaries... Europeans call the emperor, king, Dooku, prince, president, kenaz and others dictionaries."

In this section, the author also reflects on the laws of European countries, the way of life of different peoples, kings and ministers, management organizations.

The next topic covered in the textbook is called "religion and customs". In it, the author reflects on the religions in which all peoples believe, on several confessions of religions, paganism, Christianity, Islam.

The textbook also covers the topic "Measure - scale, means - money", which examines the inventions of French scientists, vertical and meridian lines on maps, ways to determine the scale. The author describes the area of the cities of Russia, Samarkand, Ferghana, Tashkent, in which km.by meridian and in which km. using examples, he explains what lies vertically.

The tutorial also has a number of applications. For example: the dates of events in world history from the Egyptian events of 4,500 years before emigration to the opening of the State Duma of Russia in 1906 are given under the heading "an example from history". Also on special pages there are separate maps "Europe", "Asia", "Africa", "north of Amricioia", "south of Amricioia", "Australia", "country of Russia", hemispheres of the earth's crust. The textbook also presents geographical forms of bays, straits, rivers and lakes, natural phenomena, various pictures explaining the movement of celestial bodies, drawings distinguishing races.

In 1906, reviews of the textbook were given on the pages of the Turkestan provincial newspaper, while some reviewers gave a positive conclusion to the textbook, while others condemned it. In particular, an employee of this newspaper, Mullah Alim, complains about the weight of the language of Mahmudhoja Behbudi's books.

In our opinion, the merits of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who is called the "father of the Turkestan Jadids", in the field of education are enormous. He supervised the opening of new schools, the creation of textbooks and teaching aids taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of children, gave lessons to other intellectuals in this field. He even opened a publishing house called "Behbudi publishing house", in which he published textbooks and textbooks for schools.

The need to teach the achievements of science for the perfection of the Behbudi nation correctly emphasized the oppression of the people who do not know science by other peoples.

As we know, the Jadids showed enlightenment, patriotism, courage on the way to the perfection of the nation. However, the content and essence of their actions, the goal and the task were interpreted both at that time and in Soviet times with a selfish purpose. In Central Asia, the early Renaissance originated in the IX-XII centuries, the scientific and cultural rise of this century was manifested by the example of the Mamun Academy. The second Renaissance occurred during the reign of Timur and the Timurids, during this period the great state building (the kingdom of Amur Timur), the great miracle of the XV century, built by Mirzo Ulugbek, the bright star

Observatory-a vivid example of the scientific thought of that time. After the fourth century, the Jadid intelligentsia gave birth to the third process of national revival. They created the first textbooks in this field, justifying the need for a modern academic discipline of geography along with other socio-political disciplines.

Behbudi made a worthy contribution to the formation of the national geographic education. His textbook "map of Turkestan" and articles on the need to teach students knowledge in the field of geography are important. The level of textbooks created by Behbudi is high from the point of view of that time, and has important didactic significance for our days. To create a modern textbook, it is advisable that methodologists and teachers of the aspiring century in their practical activities use the scientific and methodological approaches outlined in these textbooks. However, the language of textbooks is somewhat complicated, it is also worth considering that the number of Arabic and Persian words in them is extremely large, some words are incomprehensible.

The cultural - spiritual and scientific-pedagogical heritage of our ancestors is ancient and rich. Understanding our national values, forming a national idea and ideology in the minds of the people is one of the most relevant tasks of the present day.

REFERENCES

1. Ахрарова З.Б. Махмудхўжа Бехбудийнинг педагогик қарашлари ва маърифий Амалий фаолияти. Пед. фан. номз. илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган дисс. ... – Тошкент: 1997, – 195 б.
2. Намроев Ш. Е. Boshlang`ich ta`limda jadidlar merosidan foydalanish. O`quv qo`llanma. Qarshi:"Intellekt", 2023, -239 b.
3. Қосимов Б. Миллий уйғониш. Т.: «Маънавият», 2002, -400 б.
4. Қосимов Б., Юсупов Ш., Долимов У. ва бошқалар. Миллий уйғониш даври ўзбек адабиёти. Т.: «Маънавият», 2004, -464 б.
5. Намроев Ш. Е. Boshlang`ich sinflarda jadidlar merosidan foydalanish. Monografiya. Qarshi:"Fan va ta`lim", 2021, -216 b.
6. Ҳамроев Ш.Э., Каримов Б. П., Муҳаммадиев Ш. М. “Жадидларнинг дарсликларидаги бадий матнлар асосида бошланғич синф ўқувчиларини ахлоқий тарбиялаш” Монография. Қарши:"Фан ва таълим", 2021, -186 б.